

Appendix I

Final do/be/feel goals and the roles captured from e-workshops

Roles	Do goals	Be goals	Feel goals
Average users	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I want to be able to edit my stories on Facebook Messenger. Sometimes it takes time to delete them and recreate them again. So it would be cool if I could just edit them and then reshare them again. 2. I want to have a chance to immediately delete advertising messages from 3rd parties without even seeing them 3. I want to be able to send messages to a secret chat, so no one sees or reads whatever I send 4. I want to be able to pay via Facebook Messenger 5. I want to be able to delete others' messages 6. I want other people to be constrained from deleting my messages however 7. I want to be able to scan and translate whatever I need from Messenger 8. I want to select how long people can see my moments/stories 9. I want to turn Voice Messages into Texts 10. I want to get just relevant ads for my needs only, like being able to filter ads before they appear in my messenger. 11. I would say that I wouldn't like to be able to play all kinds of games on the Facebook Messenger platform. I think it would be good if the gaming feature was fully removed from the messenger. In my opinion, it is a waste of time. 12. I want to be able to send large size documents via Messenger 13. I want Facebook messenger to be as basic as possible, now it is too overloaded. It's better to have a few functions like calling, messaging and sharing stories. 14. I want to be able to play all kinds of games on the Facebook Messenger platform. Like, be able to integrate all browser games to Messenger with one click 15. I want ads to be automatically blocked while I'm playing games with my friends on Messenger 16. I want to be able to restrict some people from seeing my current location, or any information related to me 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I would say it would be cool if this action was ubiquitous, like being present everywhere at once, so I can edit it not only from Facebook messenger but also from other platforms that relate to Facebook. 2. I want it to be easy to do and transparent, especially being easily understood or seen through (because of a lack of subtlety) 3. I want his function to be cryptographic and high-quality. 4. I want it to be secure and fast 5. I want it to be inconspicuous and fast 6. I want it to be well protected 7. I want it to be fast and flawless 8. I want this function to be fast and secure 9. I want it to be protected and intuitive 10. I'd like this function to be more secure, filtered, so I don't see irrelevant information. 11. I want it to be large-scale, applied to all accounts, wide, common, automatic, and safe 12. I want it to be fast and applied to all platforms 13. I want it to be easy to use and to understand 14. I want it to be optimized, and benevolent, and easy, fast to do 15. Automatic and configured 16. I want it to be secure and easy to do 17. I want it to be automatic 18. I want it to be just fast and in good condition 19. I want it to be easy to set up 20. I want it to be fast and easy to use 21. I want it to be secure and fast 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I want to feel confident that the story that I shared was changed, and no one noticed it at the end. 2. I want to feel empowered that I don't get those messages, and I'm in charge of changing it. 3. I want to feel assured, safe and strong, that nobody reads my messages except me and the person who received my message. 4. I want to feel tech-savvy, carefree, and unrestrained, and empowered 5. I want to feel forceful and dominant and free of the need for affirmation by others. 6. I want my opinions to be accepted and appreciated by others, so they won't be able to delete them 7. I want to feel assured and optimistic that whenever I want I can access this function in messenger and translate everything I need easily. And also, I want to be understood. For example, when I use this function, I want it to translate anything without any errors, thus the opposite side understands me correctly. 8. I want to create the FOMO effect, so people miss my moments and try to check my moments every time in order not to miss them. I want to feel appreciated, cherished, and valued. 9. I want to feel relieved of the burden of writing long text messages and recording voice messages, I also want to feel loved, communal, and appreciated by people who don't like to listen to long audio messages 10. I want to feel more well-informed, but at the same time, not being bombarded with lots of unrelated ads. I have nothing against ads, I just hate when they are irrelevant, so that is why I want to feel relatable and free. 11. I want to feel more realistic, less or noncompetitive at all, to feel present and spend time with friends in a more meaningful way, not just playing some games over messenger. 12. I want to feel unchained and capable 13. I want to feel calm, a little bit isolated from unnecessary things. 14. I want to feel engaged, imaginative, competitive, fictional, and joyful, and also connected with my friends around the same things, interests 15. I want to feel more forceful, involved,

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 17. I want to be able to schedule my messages 18. I want voice messages to be longer than 1 minute 19. I want to be able to spend less time in Messenger, be able to lock it 20. I want to be able to reach out to my close friends faster, in 1 click 21. I want to be able to post content on my friends' "stories." 		<p>respectful, and conscious, so no ads bombard my phone while I'm playing games</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 16. I want to feel free, safe, and unoccupied 17. I want to feel caring, supportive, and responsible. I want people to realize how much I care about them. Maybe I even want to feel accepted by them 18. I want to feel free again and be able to record my voice properly, so no one gets bothered when i send 5 voice messages in a row for 1 minute 19. I want to feel free, relieved, and more realistic, not being in a virtual world 20. I want to feel that I didn't spend much time in order to find close people in the messenger app, and also I want them to feel special, and I also want to feel special if someone adds me to the close contact list 21. I want to feel engaged, happy and joyful
<p>Government representative</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I want to be able to see and read all the messages from all chats. 2. I want to be able to listen to all voice messages as well 3. I want to get all the detailed information about the person who has sent the message 4. I want to see the messages of all users. 5. I want to be able to see all messages/moments and etc., which have been edited and want to see originals before they have been edited. 6. I want to see all transactions which were done by using Facebook Messenger 7. I want to be able to restrict some games on Facebook Messenger, so people can't play whatever they want 8. I would like to be able to see and block all dangerous ads for users 9. I want to be able to impact people choices 10. I want to be able to listen to the voice calls via messenger 11. I want to be able to have a function which automatically blocks dangerous ads 12. I want to be able to make messages from 3rd parties go to the spam folder 13. I want to restrict advertisers to be able to do extensive targeting, as Joanna mentioned 14. I want to be able to restrict the Facebook Messenger app for a specific person if it is needed 15. I would like the government to be in charge of all the chatbots, or other automatic functions within messenger, in order to prevent all 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I want this function to be seamless, fast, and secure 2. I want this function to be fast and secure 3. I want it to be fast, cheap, and flawless 4. I want this process to be fast, secure, and easy 5. I want this function to be fast, accessible for a long run 6. I want it to be intuitive and precise 7. I want it to be fast, easy to use, safe, automatic 8. I want it to be secure, transparent, and protected 9. I want it to be seamless, and cryptographic 10. I want it to be secure, invisible 11. I want it to be automatic and fast 12. I want it to be cryptographic and logical 13. I want it to be protective and encrypted, so no one could avoid or hack it 14. I want it to be fast, and I don't want other people to know about this feature, I want it to be a secret 15. I want it to be proprietary, protective, and secure 16. I want it to be cross-functional, fast, secure 17. I want it to be fast, seamless, and collaborative 18. I want this to be fast and precise 19. I want it to be secure, fast 20. I want it to be secure and 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I want to feel well informed, knowledgeable and empowered at the same time, so I can access all messages that I want to read. 2. I want to feel in control of everything and impetuous 3. I want to feel rational, affectional and alarmed 4. I want to feel highly informed and want to control everything that goes around. 5. I want to feel assured and secure and, at the same time, confident that I can control the situation again and have an overview of what has been posted or what was edited or deleted. 6. I want to feel dominant, in control, and undismayed 7. I want to feel assured that no one gets hurt, I want to feel in control of everything, powerful, secure, and unattached 8. I want to feel powerful, in charge, and in control of everything 9. I want to feel supreme and authoritative 10. I want to be sure of myself, and prepotent 11. I want to feel impactful, dominant, and ruling 12. I want to feel self-indulgent and protected 13. I want to feel ruling and successful in my career as well since I serve people's needs 14. I want to feel strong and farsighted 15. I want to feel in control, helpful, and powerful 16. I want to feel dominant, smart, secure, protective, and backed up with data and enough resources 17. I want to feel close up and well-informed

	<p>kinds of fraud.</p> <p>16. I want to be able to listen to all voice messages and actually convert them to text format, so it would be easier for me to track and see everything</p> <p>17. I want to be able to see people location if they don't even share it</p> <p>18. I want to be able to get information about people's behavior, like what they watch, what they are interested in, what they are doing on a daily basis, etc.</p> <p>19. I want to have access to secret conversations</p> <p>20. I want to have access to people's rooms, which they create in order to have group calls</p>	<p>fast</p>	<p>18. I definitely want to feel assertive and governing</p> <p>19. I want to feel determined and aware</p> <p>20. I want to feel decisive, in touch, and influential</p>
<p>Advertisers</p>	<p>1. I want to be able to build customer loyalty</p> <p>2. I want to be able to attract potential customers</p> <p>3. I want to be able to stream geo-localized marketing services at the bottom of chats and online games that are specifically tailored to the users' preferences</p> <p>4. I want to be able to charge customers via Messenger</p> <p>5. I also want to be able to impact people choices</p> <p>6. I want to be able to show ads to users even during video calls</p> <p>7. I would like to be able to avoid ad blocking on messenger by 3rd parties</p> <p>8. I want to be able to engage with my customers, to get to know them better in order to create individual ads for each user</p> <p>9. I want to send messages to all or selected page's followers by one button, actually it can be paid function, as advertising</p> <p>10. I want to listen to voice messages easier as we can do it in WhatsApp Messenger</p> <p>11. I want to cross-sell and up-sell my products and services</p> <p>12. I want to be able to target users on Messenger based on their recent behaviors, such as if they've traveled outside of the country or if they've searched a particular keyword recently, downloaded an App, read an article on the topic.</p> <p>13. I want to target non-brand-aware users.</p> <p>14. I don't want to bother my customers with notifications, I want to use the same ads which are evenly tailored to all users so they don't get frustrated</p> <p>15. I want to be able to sell services via chatbots or be in touch with my clients using chatbots</p>	<p>1. I want it to be fast and effective</p> <p>2. I want it to be easy to use and optimized</p> <p>3. I want this function to be assistive and intuitive, also I want it to be very precise</p> <p>4. I want this function to be flawless, easy to use, fast and secure</p> <p>5. I want it to be complete, without any errors, and not noticeable for users</p> <p>6. I want it to be transparent and intuitive</p> <p>7. I'd like this function to be well protected, and easy to implement, and also cross-functional</p> <p>8. I'd like this function to be secure but at the same time seamless and very intuitive</p> <p>9. I want it to connect with my clients faster. Because when you send messages to clients one by one, you can't approach them as fast as you want it to be</p> <p>10. I want it to be easier to explain to the client by audio messages, but it can be not comfortable for the client if they don't have headphones</p> <p>11. I want it to be flawless and very intuitive, so I don't spend much time trying to figure out how it works. It would be great if it also shows me what kind of steps I need to take in order to set up a cross-selling function</p> <p>12. I want it to be secure and easy to achieve</p> <p>13. I want it to be manageable, usable and safe</p>	<p>1. I want to feel appreciated, communal, and accepted</p> <p>2. I want to feel famous, very well known and loved</p> <p>3. I want to feel heard, helpful, powerful, conscious and listened to more often than ever.</p> <p>4. I want to feel empowered, understood, and heeded</p> <p>5. I want to feel helpful, assistive, and caring</p> <p>6. I want to feel presiding and omnipresent</p> <p>7. I want to feel successful, assured, free, and empowered that I reached my end users without any problems</p> <p>8. I want to feel wholesome, communal, and connected to my clients</p> <p>9. I want to feel comfortable that my message would approach all my followers</p> <p>10. I want to feel more comfortable and closer to a client</p> <p>11. I want to feel listened to</p> <p>12. I want to feel fulfilled that i reached out to enough amount of people, subservient, like prepared to obey my customers unquestioningly and successful in my career</p> <p>13. I want to feel assured that I reached out to more people than before, and I also want others to be influenced, I myself want to have an influence on them.</p> <p>14. I want to feel very individual and independent</p> <p>15. I want to feel free, careless, being sure that chatbots may engage my customers and answer their questions</p> <p>16. I want to feel fulfilled and successful</p> <p>17. I want to feel heard, to be listened to, to get connected with more people, to stand out as an advertiser</p> <p>18. I want to feel powerful, self-governing, and also smart</p> <p>19. I want to feel frugal, omnipresent, and useful</p>

	<ol style="list-style-type: none">16. I want my ads to reach out to more people with a single click17. I want to be able to host webinars, online events18. I want to be able to avoid ad blockers19. I want to be able to create a "circle" of customers to chat with them	<ol style="list-style-type: none">14. I want this function to be cross-functional and available in 1 click15. I want it to be secure and human, so people do not feel that they are talking to robots16. I want this function to be easy to use in terms of user experience17. I want this function to be cross-functional and powerful so that it can host more than 500+ people, for example18. I want it to be safe and fast19. I want it to be cross-functional and flexible	
--	--	---	--